

Pre-Pottery Neolithic in the Near East

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The Pre-Pottery Neolithic group assemblage refers to the communities that settled in the early Holocene territories of Southwest Asia from about the 10th millennium until the middle of the 7th millennium. These Neolithic groups are primarily spread across the area known as the Fertile Crescent, i.e., the Levant, Anatolia, and Mesopotamia. Among the most significant socio-economic developments of this prehistoric transition are the construction of permanent public structures and monuments, the intensive cultivation of plants and animals (some of which become domesticated), and the establishment of domestic modes of food production. Communities begin to be less nomadic and more sedentary, establishing a more robust and extensive network of social relationships based on trade and the exchange of goods, social practices, and ideas. These developments are generally classified into two chronological phases: the Pre-Pottery Neolithic A (PPNA), which lasts from approximately 9700 to 8600 BCE, and the last phases of the Pre-Pottery Neolithic, the PPNB-C, which begins in 8500 and lasts until 6600 BCE. Many of the social transformations that characterized this prehistoric period occur in the PPNB, such as the emergence of a series of large settlements, the adoption of agro-pastoral activities, and the construction of compartmentalised rectilinear structures. Finally, one of the most prominent features of the Pre-Pottery Neolithic is the formation of built environments rich in figural representations and symbols dedicated to ritual practices, socialisation, and perhaps religious performances. On many occasions, ritual forms are related to burials as in the case of the detachment, manipulation, and decoration of human skulls.

Date Range: 9700 BCE - 6600 BCE

Region: South-west Asia

Region tags: Anatolia, Syria, Palestine, Jordan, Asia Minor, Iran, Turkey, Levant, Iraq, Northern Iraq, Israel, Middle East, Lebanon

The region of south-west Asia encompasses the territories from the Sinai Peninsula, the Saudi Arabian desert up to the Black and Caspian seas and from the Anatolia region to the Zagros Mountains.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cauvin, J. (2000). *The Birth of the Gods and the Origins of Agriculture*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Source 2: Hodder, I. (Ed.) (2014). *Religion at work in a neolithic society : vital matters*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Source 3: Kuijt, I. (Ed.) (2002). *Life in Neolithic farming communities: social organization, identity, and differentiation*. New York Boston Dordrecht London Moscow: Kluwer Academic Publishers.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://www.exoriente.org/associated_projects/ppnd.php

– Source 1 Description: Online Platform for Neolithic periods and radiocarbon dates by Ex Oriente

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.dainst.blog/the-tepe-telegrams/>

– Source 2 Description: The Tepe Telegrams. News and publications about Göbekli Tepe edited by the German Archaeological Institute

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: There are many groups developing during the PPN transition. The main clusters are located in the southern Levant, northern Mesopotamia, south-eastern Anatolia, southern Mesopotamia and the Zagros. Neolithic communities in the Near East are in relatively frequent contact as evidenced by the exchange of artifacts (e.g. obsidians), cultural practices (e.g. skull depositions), and craft expertise.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough archaeological evidence to suggest competition between PPN groups

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence to suggest PPN groups were accommodating or pluralistic. Conflict and warfare are social phenomena that cannot be excluded in this prehistoric period.

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence to suggest PPN groups were neutral. Conflict and warfare are social phenomena that cannot be excluded in this prehistoric period.

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough archaeological evidence to suggest violent conflicts between PPN groups. Although there are some archaeological indicators that may support the practice of violent acts (e.g. blunt trauma on some human skulls), it is not clear whether these are due to natural causes, ritual practices or other reasons. See discussion on this topic in Hodder, I. (Ed.) (2019). *Violence and the Sacred in the Ancient Near East: Girardian Conversations at*

Çatalhöyük: Cambridge University Press.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough archaeological evidence to suggest violent conflicts between PPN groups. Although there are some archaeological indicators that may support the practice of violent acts (e.g. blunt trauma on some human skulls), it is not clear whether these are due to natural causes, ritual practices or other reasons. See discussion on this topic in Hodder, I. (Ed.) (2019). *Violence and the Sacred in the Ancient Near East: Girardian Conversations at Çatalhöyük*: Cambridge University Press.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: It is unlikely that PPN communities have a system in place for assigning religious affiliation. Most theories of Religion in the Neolithic are based on archaeological records which are not text-based. A system that confers religious affiliation implies the establishment of a complex system of social differentiation that is still in the very early stages of development during the early Neolithic.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No evidence seems to suggest PPN groups were actively engaged in proselytism or recruitment of new members

Does the religion have official political support

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Group affiliation, commitment and political structures are emerging social phenomena during the PPN transition. It is difficult to say whether political establishments that can be observed in some sites (for example Göbekli Tepe, Körtik Tepe and other sites in the Levant) enforced costly signaling methods and/or fostered socio-political engagement to support religious beliefs. Cf. Kim Sterelny (2020) Religion: costs, signals, and the Neolithic transition, *Religion, Brain & Behavior*, 10:3, 303-320, DOI: 10.1080/2153599X.2019.1678513. See also Dietrich et al 2019 "Markers of 'Psychocultural' Change. The early-Neolithic monuments of Göbekli Tepe in southeastern Turkey" in *Handbook of Cognitive Archaeology. Psychology in Prehistory*, edited by Tracy B. Henley, Matt J. Rossano, and Edward P. Kardas (Routledge): pp. 311-332

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The concept of apostasy is unlikely to have been fully developed in Neolithic societies, since it implies an acceptance/rejection of certain religious doctrines and conventions that most probably did not yet exist. Although it cannot be excluded that members of a group publicly abandoned certain traditions, it is difficult to support such a claim through archaeological evidence.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Estimating population levels in prehistory is notoriously difficult. Many methods can be applied for demographic analysis including DNA mutation rates and counting the number of houses, artifacts, and sites. It could be that some large PPN settlements were hosting hundreds, if not thousands, of co-resident individuals, although such estimates are affected by a number of methodological challenges such as building density and contemporaneity, assessment of building typology and degree of representativeness of excavated areas. For further information see Birch-Chapman, S. (2017). Estimating population parameters of early villages in the Pre-Pottery Neolithic Central and Southern Levant. (PhD dissertation), Bournemouth University; Palmisano, A., Lawrence, D., de Gruchy, M. W., Bevan, A., & Shennan, S. (2021). Holocene regional population dynamics and climatic trends in the Near East: A first comparison using archaeo- demographic proxies. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 252, 106739.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Estimating population levels in prehistory is notoriously difficult. Many methods can be applied for demographic analysis including DNA mutation rates and counting the number of houses, artifacts, and sites. It could be that some large PPN settlements were hosting hundreds, if not thousands, of co-resident individuals, although such estimates are affected by a number of methodological challenges such as building density and contemporaneity, assessment of building typology and degree of representativeness of excavated areas. For further information see Birch-Chapman, S. (2017). Estimating population parameters of early villages in the Pre-Pottery Neolithic Central and Southern Levant. (PhD dissertation), Bournemouth University; Palmisano, A., Lawrence, D., de Gruchy, M. W., Bevan, A., & Shennan, S. (2021). Holocene regional population dynamics and climatic trends in the Near East: A first comparison using archaeo- demographic proxies. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 252, 106739.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Monuments are important architectural features emerging from the Neolithic period. The most famous examples are the tower of Jericho, the enclosures of pillars at Göbekli Tepe, Karahan Tepe and other sites in the Urfa region.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This calculation is difficult to pursue. The issues are mostly due to the typology of the sites and monuments (i.e. whether they are for religious purposes or not) and excavated area. Many of the PPN settlements are only a small percentage of the area excavated.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Mortuary rituals are common in the Neolithic. Notably sites like Kfar Hahoreh in the southern Levant, Körtik Tepe and Çayönü in Anatolia present architectural features related to burials that might be considered as monumental.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A significantly high number of burials is seen in certain sites (e.g. Körtik Tepe). However, it is difficult to say whether these burial areas can be considered proper cemeteries. It is important to note that some buildings were dedicated to mortuary practices (e.g. the skull building at Çayönü, the Maison des Morts at Djade, building 5 at Bestansur)

↳ Temples:

– I don't know

Notes: Using such terminology might not be appropriate for this period

↳ Altars:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Possibly. The tower of Jericho could be considered a landscape marker for local communities. See Bar-Yosef, O. (1986). The walls of Jericho: an alternative interpretation. *Current anthropology*, 27(2), 157-162. Ronen, A., & Adler, D. (2001). The walls of Jericho were magical. *Archaeology, ethnology and anthropology of Eurasia*, 2(6), 97-103. Naveh, D. (2003). PPNA Jericho: a socio-political perspective. *Cambridge Archaeological Journal*, 13(1), 83-96.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Special Purpose Building Area at Aşıklı Höyük is characterised by a set of large buildings, storing structures and a courtyard that are significantly different from the standard buildings located in other areas. Differentiation in the architectural layout is also noticed at Çayönü between the eastern and the western sides of the settlement. These cases could be considered mass gathering points however further research is needed to sustain such interpretation.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As archaeological investigations proceed, other monuments possibly associated with religious beliefs can emerge.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Figural representations are present in both unordinary buildings as well as in houses through the manufacture of 3D artifacts, reliefs, paintings, or inscriptions.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Difficult to distinguish features in the iconography dedicated to religious purposes. There are certain traditions in the figural representation observed in certain geographical areas (e.g. a particular emphasis in the representation of wild animals in the northern Levant and south-eastern Anatolia) but this may simply be due to cultural trends and not religious behavior.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not. Initially, sites like Göbekli Tepe were considered as unique sacred places, but current ongoing archaeological investigations seem to suggest otherwise. See also discussion on this topic in Banning, E. B. (2011). So Fair a House. *Current anthropology*, 52(5), 619-660.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some have argued that sites like Göbekli Tepe were centres of congregation for local communities (see for example Renfrew, C. (2013). Centres of Congregation. *NEO-LITHICS* 2/13), but this is debated.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The fact that mortuary practices in the Neolithic are quite elaborated and often associated with artistic depictions or special architectural features suggest that a consciousness of the spirit-body distinction is most likely present during this prehistoric phase

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably the Neolithic populations had a conception of the difference of power of the spirit-mind. The beliefs that some objects had magical properties have been supported by some authors (see Gebel, H. G. K., Hermansen, B. D., & Jensen, C. H. (Eds.). (2002). *Magic practices and ritual in the Near Eastern Neolithic : proceedings of a workshop held at the 2nd International Congress on the Archaeology of the Ancient Near East (ICAANE)*, Copenhagen University, May 2000. Berlin: Ex Oriente)

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Shamanism is one of the interpretations of the ritual forms that has been put forward by some authors (see for instance Benz, M., & Bauer, J. (2015). *On scorpions, birds and snakes—Evidence for shamanism in Northern Mesopotamia during the Early Holocene*. *Journal of Ritual Studies*, 1-23)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Detecting differences in PPN burial treatment is a challenging task as it is rarely evidenced in archaeological records.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sacrifices in graves are not an obvious practice in the Neolithic. Although animal bones and other scattered human remains are sometimes seen in relation to burial, associating such evidence with the practice of sacrifice can be speculative and problematic as cutmarks on animal bones may be a sign of feasting and cutmarks on human bones have been interpreted as defleshing practices as part of ritual forms (see in this regard Pilloud, M. A., Haddow, S. D., Knüsel, C. J., & Larsen, C. S. (2016). A bioarchaeological and forensic re-assessment of vulture defleshing and mortuary practices at Neolithic Çatalhöyük. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, 10, 735-743).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Grave goods are not common in the PPN but there are occasionally seen. Fragments of decorated objects are buried with the dead at Körtik Tepe and beads are also seen in graves (e.g. Bestansur)

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to being evidence of long-distance trade and networking, the carnelian beads found in Neolithic burials at Bestansur in Iraq could be considered valuable objects. See Matthews, R., Matthews, W., Richardson, A., Walsh, S., Iversen, I., Mudd, D., ... & Elliott, S. (2019). The early Neolithic of Iraqi Kurdistan: Current research at Bestansur, Shahrizor plain. *Paléorient. Revue pluridisciplinaire de préhistoire et de protohistoire de l'Asie du Sud-Ouest et de l'Asie centrale*, (45-2), 13-32.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Depending on how significant the value of some buried items is for Neolithic people (which in itself is difficult to assess), some worked objects (e.g. decorated portable objects found in the grave of Körtik Tepe) could be considered as wealthy products

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Depending on how significant the value of some buried items is for Neolithic people (which in itself is difficult to assess), some worked objects (e.g. decorated portable objects found in the grave of Körtik Tepe) could be considered as wealthy

products

Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: beads and decorated portable objects

Notes: Depending on how significant the value of some buried items is for Neolithic people (which in itself is difficult to assess), some worked objects (e.g. decorated portable objects found in the grave of Körtik Tepe) could be considered as wealthy products

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Significant differences in burial treatment within a community are rarely seen in the PPN. This topic is under discussion. Nevertheless, there are some cases where inequality in depositional patterns can be argued. See for example Benz, M., Gresky, J., & Alarashi, H. (2020). Similar but different: displaying social roles of subadults in burials from the Late Pre-Pottery Neolithic site of Baja, Southern Jordan. In H. Alarashi & R. M. Dessì (Eds.), *The art of human appearance : from prehistory to the present day* (pp. 93-107). Nice: Éditions APDCA.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is a hotly debated question. E.g. whether the stylised T-shaped human representations are actually a reference to supernatural beings or ancestors is under discussion

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In light of the emergence of the first large villages in the PPN, the idea of implementing symbolic forms of social control has been the subject of discussion recently (see Norenzayan, Ara. "Does religion make people moral?." *Behaviour* 151.2-3 (2014): 365-384)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: some have argued that the depictions of wild and dangerous animals, which are commonly found in many sites, represent an intent to implement a psychological influence in order to strengthen group membership (see for example). Such images could also be interpreted as a form of deterrence and/or punishment against free-riders

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough archaeological evidence to support that Neolithic individuals had a belief in supernatural forces who bestow rewards.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: social conventions and norms are social realities most likely already structured during the PPN transition but it is not certain whether these were prescribed by religious beliefs

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: probably the distinction between cultural conventions and moral values was not established in the Neolithic yet

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No evidence suggests the practice of celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Symbols of sexuality (e.g. phallic depictions) are seen in both the early and late phases of the Neolithic. However, it is not known whether these were meant to monitor sexual activities

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Symbols of sexuality (e.g. phallic depictions) are seen in both the early and late phases of the Neolithic. However, it is not known whether these forms of representation were associated with

cultural practices aimed at altering the sexual organs.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence suggests the practice of fasting during the Neolithic although such cultural practice cannot be excluded

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Taboos are cultural aspects that may have been part of the Neolithic world (see for instance Russell, Nerissa. "Feathers and talons: birds at Neolithic Çatalhöyük, Turkey." *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences* 11.12 (2019): 6393-6410.). However, if there were taboos, it is not known whether these were supported by religious belief.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Defleshing and post-mortem body modifications are evident in many buried human bones. Scarring and bodily alterations might have occurred during the Neolithic but it is unclear whether these were done intentionally for religious purposes.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence seems to indicate the practice of painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds, although this aspect cannot be excluded as violence and rituals involving the depiction of wild and dangerous animals and the manipulation of human bones are part of the socio-cultural background in many PPN communities

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Violence and rituals involving the depiction of wild and dangerous animals and the manipulation of human bones are part of the socio-cultural background in many PPN communities. The deposition of bones in the proximity of architectural features could be interpreted as foundation deposits involving the human sacrifice (see Moses, Sharon. "Sociopolitical implications of Neolithic foundation deposits and the possibility of child sacrifice: A case study at Çatalhöyük, Turkey." *Sacred Killing: The Archaeology of Sacrifice in the Ancient Near East*. Winona Lake, Ind.: Eisenbrauns (2012): 57-77).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Violence and rituals involving the depiction of wild and dangerous animals and the manipulation of human bones are part of the socio-cultural background in many PPN communities. The deposition of bones in the proximity of architectural features could be interpreted as foundation deposits involving the human sacrifice (see Moses, Sharon. "Sociopolitical implications of Neolithic foundation deposits and the possibility of child sacrifice: A case study at Çatalhöyük, Turkey." *Sacred Killing: The Archaeology of Sacrifice in the Ancient Near East*. Winona Lake, Ind.: Eisenbrauns (2012): 57-77).

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence seems to indicate the practice of suicide, although this aspect cannot be excluded as violence and rituals involving the depiction of wild and dangerous animals and the manipulation of human bones are part of the socio-cultural background in many PPN communities

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Intentionally deposition of objects such as figurines and obsidians below floors, postholes or near other architectural installations could indicate that these were valuable items or seen as entities possessing agency. In turn, it can be speculated that some individuals had had to give up these objects and use them for different purposes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is insufficient archaeological evidence to answer this question. Attending meetings or investing heavily in the construction of monuments could be seen as a sacrifice of time.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Violence and rituals involving the depiction of wild and dangerous animals and the manipulation of human bones are part of the socio-cultural background in many PPN communities. So it cannot be excluded that some ritual forms required taking physical risks.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably there were no structured and fixed ethical principles established by the religious groups to be formally accepted by members. But moral precepts might have been emerging in some communities during the PPN transition

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: The archaeological evidence seems to point to an opposite cultural behavior that is the cohesion and inclusion of group members rather than marginalization

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Both household rituals were foreseen in many PPN communities. See for example the case of Boncuklu in Baird, D., Fairbairn, A., & Martin, L. (2017). The animate house, the institutionalization of the household in Neolithic central Anatolia. *World Archaeology*, 49(5), 753-776.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Feasting and ceremonies (many related to mortuary rituals) are evidenced by architectural evidence but also by faunal remains.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The number of participants varies from site to site. For Gobekli Tepe estimates see McBride, A. S. (2012). Multi-sensual analysis of near eastern neolithic communal architecture and the implications for communities (Doctoral dissertation, University of Liverpool).

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is insufficient archaeological evidence to answer this question.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is insufficient archaeological evidence to answer this question.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The PPN transition bears witness to one of the most important social transformations in prehistory. Hunter-gatherer communities began to change their lifeway. They went from being small communities of less than 100 individuals to forming large villages of hundreds of people.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known whether an institutionalized welfare system was established during the Neolithic period. On the other hand, more or less structured systems of community support probably existed.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known whether an institutionalized welfare system was established during the Neolithic period. On the other hand, more or less structured systems of community support probably existed.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known whether an institutionalized welfare system was established during the Neolithic period. On the other hand, more or less structured systems of community support probably existed.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known whether an institutionalized welfare system was established during the Neolithic period. On the other hand, more or less structured systems of community support probably existed.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known whether an institutionalized welfare system was established during the Neolithic period. On the other hand, more or less structured systems of community support probably existed.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known whether an institutionalized welfare system was established during the Neolithic period. On the other hand, more or less structured systems of community support probably existed.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: It is unlikely that formal bureaucracy emerged during the PPN

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Notes: It is unlikely that formal bureaucracy emerged during the PPN

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The administration of food resources changes during the Neolithic and it is unclear whether the religious group(s) managed these resources. While at the beginning of the PPN food storage is prevalently communal (e.g. Dhra'), evidence of domestic modes of food procurement and storage emerges particularly in the PPNB. See Kuijt, I. (2011). Home is where we keep our food: The origins of agriculture and late Pre-Pottery Neolithic food storage. *Paléorient*, 137-152.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The administration of food resources changes during the Neolithic and it is unclear whether the religious group(s) managed these resources. While at the beginning of the PPN food storage is prevalently communal (e.g. Dhra'), evidence of domestic modes of food procurement and storage emerges particularly in the PPNB. See Kuijt, I. (2011). Home is where we keep our food: The origins of agriculture and late Pre-Pottery Neolithic food storage. *Paléorient*, 137-152.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Fully developed irrigation and flood control systems only appear in later prehistoric periods. During the Neolithic period, there are some archaeological indicators of water management, particularly at sites not located near water sources (e.g. Ba'ja). It is not clear whether the religious group(s) administered water. See Gebel, H. G. K. (2010). The commodification of water. *Neo-Lithics*, 2(10), 4-13.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Fully developed irrigation and flood control systems only appear in later prehistoric periods. During the Neolithic period, there are some archaeological indicators of water management,

particularly at sites not located near water sources (e.g. Ba'ja). It is not clear whether the religious group(s) or other formal institutions administered water. See Gebel, H. G. K. (2010). The commodification of water. *Neo-Lithics*, 2(10), 4-13.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: No clear archaeological evidence of transportation infrastructure run by groups of elite or religious (or non-religious) institutions is noted during the PPN

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No clear archaeological evidence of transportation infrastructure run by groups of elite or religious (or non-religious) institutions is noted during the PPN

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unlikely that Neolithic groups implemented a structured system of taxation or tithes, particularly during the early stages of the PPN when the sharing of goods and resources is much more evident and the unequal division of power and property was nearly absent

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unlikely that Neolithic groups implemented a structured system of taxation or tithes, particularly during the early stages of the PPN when the sharing of goods and resources is much more evident and the unequal division of power and property was nearly absent

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: more or less formal judicial systems may have been established to foster cooperation in some large communities but this is difficult to observe in the Neolithic archaeological records.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: more or less formal judicial systems may have been established to foster cooperation in some large communities but this is difficult to observe in the Neolithic archaeological records.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Violence and public punishment might have been carried out in some communities against free-riders or individuals who violate cultural norms and conventions. Nevertheless, it is unclear whether possible forms of punishment were enforced by religious entities or other social bodies.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Violence and public punishment might have been carried out in some communities against free-riders or individuals who violate cultural norms and conventions. Nevertheless, it is unclear whether possible forms of punishment were enforced by religious entities or other social bodies.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: It is unlikely that a formal legal code was established during the PPN

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: It is unlikely that a formal legal code was established during the PPN

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Few archaeological indicators suggest warfare during the PPN and it is not known whether institutionalized military corps existed, probably not. See Clare, L. (Ed.) (2010). *Neo-Lithics 1/10*. Special

Topic on Conflict and Warfare in the Near Eastern Neolithic. Berlin: ex oriente.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Few archaeological indicators suggest warfare during the PPN and it is not known whether institutionalized military corps existed, probably not. See Clare, L. (Ed.) (2010). Neo-Lithics 1/10. Special Topic on Conflict and Warfare in the Near Eastern Neolithic. Berlin: ex oriente.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: writing known as the system of permanent marks designed to record language did not exist in the Neolithic period

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: writing known as the system of permanent marks designed to record language did not exist in the Neolithic period

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: writing known as the system of permanent marks designed to record language did not exist in the Neolithic period

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Although evidence of tallies and notches on objects could be seen as systems for counting time, it is unlikely that religious groups possessed formal calendars. No evidence seems to suggest the creation of institutionalized calendars.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Although evidence of tallies and notches on objects could be seen as systems for counting time, it is unlikely that religious groups possessed formal calendars. No evidence seems to suggest the

creation of institutionalized calendars.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Systems of food production change during the PPN transition and vary from one region to another. Pastoralism and agriculture emerge towards the end of this prehistoric transition along with the domestication of some plant and animal species. Other forms of food supply such as fishing are also evident in a number of settlements. The scale of food production during the PPN is small to medium. Religious groups might also have been contribute to food administration.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Systems of food production change during the PPN transition and vary from one region to another. Pastoralism and agriculture emerge towards the end of this prehistoric transition along with the domestication of some plant and animal species. Other forms of food supply such as fishing are also evident in a number of settlements. The scale of food production during the PPN is small to medium. Religious groups might also have been contribute to food administration.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards